

FABRICATION OF 45S5 BIOACTIVE GLASS-POLYCAPROLACTONE COMPOSITE SCAFFOLDS

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SUMMARY

45S5 bioactive glass-polycaprolactone composite porous scaffolds were produced using a solution blending and salt-leaching technique. The main target was the optimisation of the fabrication parameters (such as: blending conditions; nature and amount of salt; glass weight fraction and granulometric size distribution) in order to confer a suitable porosity and composition to the composite scaffold.

Keywords: scaffold, bioactive glass, polycaprolactone, salt leaching, microstructure

INTRODUCTION

Tissue engineering is a multi-disciplinary field, which aims to apply innovative biomaterials to replace or restore ill or damaged tissues of the human body, such as skin and bones. In particular, porous scaffolds are used as temporary 3D templates to support cell attachment and proliferation during the spontaneous regeneration of natural tissues and this approach is particularly promising for the bone tissue restoration [1, 2].

However, in order to achieve this target, porous scaffolds should satisfy several challenging requirements [1, 2]. First of all, scaffolds must be biocompatible and bio-resorbable; in particular, the resorbability rate should fit as much as possible the spontaneous bone regeneration rate. Moreover, they must be sterilizable, both on the surface and inside to avoid infections. The mechanical properties should be comparable with those of the natural bone tissue and they should be high enough to prevent the scaffold collapse during processing and in service [1, 2]. From a morphological point of view, scaffolds should possess an adequate porosity, with a well developed network of interconnected pores whose size should exceed 100 μm , in order to promote cell penetration, tissue ingrowth and vascularization [3]. as they should exhibit a controlled bioactivity, a bio-resorbability rate compatible with the spontaneous bone regeneration rate, a mechanical behavior comparable with that of the natural bone, a porous network suitable for cell penetration, tissue ingrowth and vascularization [3].

Since the properties and performances of scaffolds greatly depend on their microstructure (including composition and morphology), the primary goal of tissue

engineering is to achieve a tailored microstructure. Moreover, in order to satisfy as many requirements as possible, composite scaffolds may be an interesting solution. Polymer-ceramic composite scaffolds, in fact, may combine the toughness, reliability and slow-rate degradation of the polymer phase with the high bioactivity of bioglasses, hydroxyapatite and other ceramic phases [2-3].

In the present contribution, polycaprolactone (PCL)-45S5 Bioglass® (Bioglass) composite scaffolds were considered, since the PCL is slowly degradable and the Bioglass is highly bioactive, so it is possible to govern the interaction rate of the scaffold with the human body by tuning the volume fractions of the constituent phases. Though some techniques are already available in the literature to produce polymer-Bioglass composite scaffolds, such as thermally induced phase separation (or freeze drying), infiltration of polymer foams and electrophoretic deposition [4-9], the composite porous scaffolds of the present research were produced using a solution blending and salt-leaching technique. Even if the salt-leaching method has been rarely adopted up-to-now [2], it offers some relevant advantages. First of all, the salt-leaching method is conceptually easy, since it creates the “voids” by simply washing out the salt. Moreover it is cost effective and it does not require specific (and expensive) equipments. The salt-leaching approach is appealing also because it does not imply any dangerous contamination, as NaCl and NaHCO₃, which are innocuous and soluble in water, can be used to create the pores.

More in detail, the present research was addressed to define the processing conditions to obtain highly porous composite scaffolds, since an optimised microstructure is a basic pre-requisite for any advanced application, especially in the biomedical context.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to achieve a well developed network of pores, the effect of various processing parameters were considered, with a particular focus on polymer molecular weight, salt type, glass particle size and respective volume fractions of the constituent phases.

PCL

The PCL is intended to provide the scaffolds with a sufficient mechanical resistance. Two different molecular weights were considered: 2000 g/mol and 65000 g/mol. In both cases, dissolving it in dichloromethane and then precipitating it in methanol and filtering purified the polymer.

Salt

Various tests were performed in order to define the best salt to use. The salt should combine a non-toxic composition and a good solubility in water; hence NaCl, NaHCO₃ and mixtures of them were evaluated. All the salts were commercially available powders.

Bioglass

The formulation of the glass (45% SiO₂, 24.5% CaO, 24.5% Na₂O, 6% P₂O₅ in weight percent) was taken from the literature [10]. The powder raw materials (Carlo Erba Reagenti, Italy) were accordingly weighted, mixed in a PE vessel for at least 1 hour and melted in a platinum crucible, heating from room temperature to 1100°C at 10°C/min, staying at 1100°C for 2 hours, heating from 1100°C to 1450°C at 10°C/min and soaking at the maximum temperature for 30 minutes. After that, the glass was poured in water to obtain a frit, which was dried in a kiln at 110°C overnight. The frit was ground in an agate jar and then, manually, in an agate mortar. The powder was sieved to separate three different grain size ranges: under 45 μm; between 45 and 75 μm; over 75 μm. Such distinction was useful to test the effect of the grain size of the glass powder on the final microstructure of the composite scaffolds. An X-ray diffraction performed on the glass powder confirmed its completely amorphous nature.

Solution blending and salt-leaching technique

The procedure followed to produce the composite scaffolds by the solution blending and salt-leaching technique can be summarized as follows:

- A fixed weight of PCL is dissolved in dichlorometane under moderate heating and stirring;
- The Bioglass powder is added in the wanted amount; the suspension is continuously stirred to prevent the glass powder precipitation;
- The salt is added as well. The stirring goes on for at least 15 minutes, to ameliorate the distribution of the constituent phases;
- The dispersion is moved into a Petri dish and the dichlorometane is left to evaporate naturally (about 1 day)
- Immersing the scaffold in distilled water washes out the salt; the water is refreshed twice every day to promote the salt dissolution.

This basic *iter* was repeated for all the samples. However, as previously mentioned, the effect of various parameters was considered:

- Molecular weight of PCL;
- Nature of salt;
- Grain size of Bioglass powder;
- Relative amount of the constituent phases.

In particular, the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) inspection revealed the consequences of the processing conditions on the microstructure of the composite porous scaffolds.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As regards the polymer “matrix”, the low-weight PCL was excluded, since the resulting scaffolds were so brittle that it was not possible to handle them. Hence, even if it is

more difficult to dissolve high-molecular weight polymers, characterized by very long molecule chains, the 65000 g/mol PCL was chosen to produce the scaffolds.

Independently of the salt employed, it was possible to produce very porous scaffolds. Nevertheless, the sample obtained using only NaHCO_3 showed relatively few and excessively large pores, with a sharp rectangular morphology. The scaffolds fabricated with NaCl (alone or mixed with NaHCO_3) were more interesting, as revealed by the SEM inspection. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the cross section and external surface of the samples obtained using only NaCl and a 50 wt% mixture of NaCl and NaHCO_3 , respectively. Both samples were produced mixing 1.1 g of PCL and 2 g of salt and adding 10% of Bioglass.

Figure 1 – Cross section (a) and external surface (b) of the porous scaffold obtained using NaCl only.

Figure 2 – Cross section (a) and external surface (b) of the porous scaffold obtained using a mixture of 50 wt% of NaCl and NaHCO_3 .

Both the scaffolds exhibited very attractive microstructures, with a porosity content not lower than 60% based on a SEM image analysis.

However, the scaffold derived from the mixture of the two salts, Figure 2, showed a very uniform thickness and a homogeneous spatial distribution of pores. Moreover, from a dimensional point of view, the pores ranged from sub-micrometric sizes (in the struts) to several tenths of microns, reaching diameter values as high as 200 μm . In addition, the SEM inspection suggested that the pores were connected, resulting in a continuous network. As a consequence, the microstructure of the sample produced with the mixture of NaCl and NaHCO₃ fully satisfied the requirements for bone tissue ingrowth and vascularization [2].

As regards the grain size of the glass particles, the finest dimensional range (<45 μm) was preferred for several reasons. First of all, large particles are more likely to precipitate during the mixing stage of the fabrication process, in spite of the continuous stirring. Moreover, small particles possess a higher specific surface and therefore are more bioactive. To conclude, fine particles are able to integrate very well into the porous polymer matrix, as shown in Figure 3, which refers to the sample obtained with < 45 μm glass particles (1.1 g of PCL; 2 g of salt, a mixture of NaCl and NaHCO₃, as previously discussed; 50% of Bioglass).

Figure 3 – Sample obtained with fine Bioglass particles (< 45 μm), which are deeply integrated into the porous polymer matrix.

The tests proved that the Bioglass content could be increased up to 75%, as exemplified by the sample shown in Figure 4 (1.1 g of PCL; 2 g of salt, mixture; 75% of Bioglass, fine powder). This is a significant achievement, since the glass amount deeply influences the interaction rate of the scaffold with the environment (i.e. human body, after implantation). As a matter of fact, while the dissolution rate of the PCL is very

low, the Bioglass is extremely bioactive. So, the opportunity of easily changing their respective amounts makes it possible to control the bioactivity of the scaffold, tailoring it to the natural growth rate of the bone tissue [1, 2].

Nevertheless, on-going tests (Thermo-Gravimetric Analysis, TGA) [11] suggest that, increasing the nominal fraction of the Bioglass, the glass powder is more likely to precipitate, reducing the effective glass fraction in the final composite. In order to avoid such precipitation phenomena, during the mixing stage the stirring must be extremely effective. Moreover, always during the mixing stage, the viscosity of the dispersion must be optimised and a balanced must be achieved, since a low viscosity is likely to favour a good and homogeneous dispersion of the glass and salt particles in the polymer-dichloromethane solution, but a high viscosity is required to limit the glass powder precipitation (especially that of the biggest particles).

As already mentioned, a deeper investigation of the materials is currently running [11].

Figure 4 – Sample obtained with 75% of Bioglass.

CONCLUSIONS

PCL-Bioglass porous composite scaffolds were produced using a solution blending and salt-leaching technique. Such method proved to be relatively easy and inexpensive. With the aim of understanding the relation existing between process parameters and scaffold microstructure, various samples were produced changing the PCL molecular

weight, the type of salt, the glass particle size and content. The accurate SEM characterization proved that working with sufficiently high molecular weight PCL (65000 g/mol), NaCl-NaHCO₃ salt mixtures and fine glass powders (< 45 µm) it is possible to obtain very promising microstructures, extremely porous, with widely differentiated pore sizes and uniformly distributed glass particles. Moreover it is possible to vary the glass amount in a very wide range, up to 75%; this should make it possible to tune the interaction rate of the porous scaffold with the human body tissues.

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